

Local Government in Ethiopia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Zemelak Ayele

CFGs - Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies
Addis Ababa University

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University
of Singapore
National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

Western
UNIVERSITY · CANADA
University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Ethiopia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

Addis Ababa University: Zemelak Ayele
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Daggy J Ali_Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Ethiopia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Ethiopia: An Introduction	8
2.2. <i>Autonomy of Local Governments</i>	11
2.3. <i>Sanitation and Hygiene Service Delivery in Urban Local Governments: A Federally Integrated Practice</i>	18
2.4. <i>Responsibilities for and Practices of Urban Land Use Planning in the City of Adama</i>	25
2.5. <i>Solid Waste Management in the City of Bahir Dar: A Matter of Capacity and Public Awareness</i> ...	34
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Ethiopia: An Introduction	39
3.2. <i>The Fiscal Equalization Scheme for Woredas</i>	43
3.3. <i>Financing Municipal Services</i>	46
3.4. <i>Financing Healthcare: The Example of the Raya-Kobo District</i>	49
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Ethiopia: An Introduction.....	55
4.2. <i>The Practice of Local Government Creation (Splitting)</i>	57
4.3. <i>Amalgamating Five Special Local Governments into a Single Administrative Zone vs Self-Government Rights of Ethnic Groups in SNNPRS</i>	61
4.4. <i>Splitting Local Government and its (Un)expected Outcomes: The Case of Amhara National Regional State</i>	67
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Ethiopia: An Introduction	73
5.2. <i>Association of Cities/Urban Forum and Urban-Rural Relations</i>	75
5.3. <i>Changing Urban Place Names in Post 2018 Amhara National Regional State: The View from Bahir Dar City</i>	85
5.4. <i>Infrastructure Projects in Addis Ababa: Between Self-Government of the Capital City and Federal Intervention</i>	91
6.1. People's Participation in Local Decision-Making in Ethiopia: An Introduction	96
6.2. <i>Participation in Urban Water Management Board in Adama/Oromia</i>	99
6.3. <i>Local Governance and Gender in Family Relations</i>	104
6.4. <i>Political Participation Along Ethnic Lines: The City of Dire Dawa</i>	108

Local Financial Arrangements

3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Ethiopia: An Introduction

Mohammed Dejen, *Centre for Federalism and Governance Studies, Addis Ababa University*

Local financial autonomy is a critical component of the overall local government autonomy. Local government without financial autonomy cannot enjoy other forms of autonomy. As McLure and Martinez-Vazquez argue, '[s]ubnational governments that lack independent sources of revenue can never truly enjoy fiscal autonomy; they may be – and probably are – under the financial thumb of the central government'.⁸³

Local financial autonomy has two elements: revenue raising and expenditure autonomy. The first is linked to local government's ability to raise revenue from internal sources by imposing taxes and charging fees for services it provides. The existence of internal sources of revenue does not count out the possibility of local government receiving revenue from senior levels of government. However, it is often suggested that local government should cover the majority of its expenditures by using revenue collected from internal sources. Moreover, at least the majority of revenue transferred to local government by the senior levels of government should be unconditional allowing local government to decide on how to spend it.⁸⁴ Expenditure autonomy has to do with local government's power to autonomously decide on how to spend the revenue it raises.

The Federal Constitution does not assign any revenue raising powers to local government as it does not also assign functional competences to the latter. The state constitutions are also vague on the revenue raising powers of local government. Indeed, under the state constitutions, *woredas* are *mandated* to assess and collect – without the power to determine the rate of – certain state taxes, such as rural land-use fees and agricultural income tax. They do so on the regional states' behalf. Thus, in principle, *woredas* are required to transfer to the regional government a certain portion of the revenue they collect from these taxes, even though in practice the latter allow *them* to retain the revenue.

In any case, *woredas* in different states raise revenue from different sources including:⁸⁵

⁸³ Charles McLure and Jorge Martinez-Vazquez, 'The Assignment of Revenues and Expenditures in Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations' (World Bank 2000) <<http://www1.worldbank.org/publicsector/decentralization/March2004Course/AssignmentRevenues.pdf>> accessed 30 December 2019.

⁸⁴ World Bank, *World Development Report 1999/2000: Entering the 21st Century* (Oxford University Press 1999) 117.

⁸⁵ Zemelak Ayele, *Local Government in Ethiopia: Advancing Development and Accommodating Ethnic Minorities* (Nomos 2014).

- income taxes from *woreda* employees and from employees of enterprises that are licensed by the *woreda*;
- taxes from small traders and traditional minors;
- user fees from libraries, clinics and community halls;
- license fees from irrigation schemes and water wells;
- fees for the registration of births, deaths, marriages and divorces.

Likewise, cities collect revenue from the following sources:

- urban land lease fees;
- land-use fees;
- municipal service fees including market fees, sanitary service, slaughterhouses, fire brigade services, mortuary and burial services, registration of birth and marriage, building plan approval, property registration and surveying, and use of municipal equipment, transport or employees;
- sale of own properties (other than land).

Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa, the two federal cities, are authorized to collect from revenue sources that normally fall within the competence of the states, these two cities do not fall within the jurisdiction of any state. They thus collect revenue by imposing income tax on their employees and on income earned from urban agricultural activities, as well as by collecting profit, excise and turnover taxes on individual traders working in the cities. They also collect revenue in the form of urban land-lease and -use fees, property rates, capital gains tax on properties in the city, stamp duties, user charges from vehicles in the city, and services charges on municipal services. Addis Ababa covers close to 97 per cent of its expenditure from internal revenue, and receives no block grant from the federal government.

As a rule, local government cannot borrow money from any source. In fact, even the states need federal approval before they can borrow revenue from domestic market and they are barred from the international market. It is not thus surprising that *woreda* and cities are barred from borrowing. Perhaps the exception in this regard are Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa which are statutorily authorized to take short- and long-term loans from domestic sources with the authorization of the federal government.⁸⁶ They may directly borrow or sell bonds, provided it does not endanger delivery of basic services.⁸⁷ Furthermore, the Addis Ababa city government may request that the federal government borrows money from international sources on its behalf.⁸⁸

As far as financial transfers are concerned, *woredas* receive conditional and unconditional grants from the states. Unconditional grants or which are also known as block grants are

⁸⁶ Art 46(1), Dire Dawa Government Charter Proclamation no 416/2004; Art 55(1), Addis Ababa City Government Revised Charter Proclamation no 361/2003.

⁸⁷ Art 46(1), FDRE Proclamation no 416/2004; Art 55(1), FDRE Proclamation no 321/2003.

⁸⁸ Art 54(3), FDRE Proclamation no 361/2003.

woredas' main source of revenue, covering up to 80 per cent of their budgets. The states set aside approximately 50 per cent of their annual budget for transferring to all *woredas* within their jurisdiction. The amount of money that a single *woreda* receives in state transfer is determined based on a preset formula.

Woredas also receive what is called special-purpose grants (SPG) which are conditional grants that the state transfer to *woredas*. State and federal governments provide financial assistance to *woredas* with respect to specific projects including projects relating to a food-security program, productive safety-net program, public service capacity-building program (PSCAB), road fund, and HIV/AIDS program. For the purpose of executing these programs, the federal government transfers SPGs to regional governments which, in turn, transfer them to local government.

Cities do not receive financial transfers from the states. They receive transfers that are meant to finance their recurrent costs relating to their state functions. The cities are required to cover the costs of providing municipal services from internal sources. The cities are thus required to administer and record municipal revenue separately from their revenue for state functions.⁸⁹ The federal government also finances specific nationally relevant projects undertaken in Addis Ababa and Dire Dawa.⁹⁰ It may assist these two federal cities financially to enable them to discharge their responsibilities.⁹¹

Before the DLDP (District Level Decentralisation Program) was launched in the early 2000s, *woredas* and cities had no expenditure autonomy. Indeed, local council could make plan and attach budget to their plans. Their plans however needed to be approved by the state executive organ. In the early 2000s, as part of the DLDP, the states revised their constitutions among other things to allow *woredas* to adopt their budget and decide on their expenditure. It should be noted however that *woredas* cover over 75 per cent of their expenditure using state transfers. As indicated above the transfers, except the SPGs, are as rule unconditional and *woredas* can decide how to spend the money they receive from the states. However, the amount that they receive is so small that it barely covers their recurrent budget. Studies show that they spend over 90 per cent of state transfers for paying salaries for their employees.⁹² This leaves them with limited expenditure autonomy.

⁸⁹ Jan Werner and David Nguyen-Thanh, 'Municipal infrastructure Delivery in Ethiopia: A Bottomless Pit or an Option to Reach the Millennium Development Goals?' (working paper 01-2007, Institute of Local Public Finance 2007) <<http://www.ilpf.de/en/download/wp-01-2007.pdf>> accessed 30 December 2019.

⁹⁰ Art 46(1), FDRE Proclamation no 416/2004 ; Art 55(1), FDRE Proclamation no 321/2003.

⁹¹ Art 46(1), FDRE Proclamation no 416/2004 ; Art 55(1), FDRE Proclamation no 321/2003.

⁹² Ayele, *Local Government in Ethiopia*, above.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Dire Dawa Government Charter Proclamation no 416/2004

Addis Ababa City Government Revised Charter Proclamation no 361/2003

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Ayele Z, *Local Government in Ethiopia: Advancing Development and Accommodating Ethnic Minorities* (Nomos 2014)

McLure C and Martinez-Vazquez J, 'The Assignment of Revenues and Expenditures in Intergovernmental Fiscal Relations' (World Bank 2000)

<<http://www1.worldbank.org/publicsector/decentralization/March2004Course/AssignmentRevenues.pdf>> last accessed 30 December 2019

Werner J and Nguyen-Thanh D, 'Municipal infrastructure Delivery in Ethiopia: A Bottomless Pit or an Option to Reach the Millennium Development Goals?' (Working Paper 01-2007, Institute of Local Public Finance 2007) <<http://www.ilpf.de/en/download/wp-01-2007.pdf>> accessed 30 December 2019

World Bank, *World Development Report 1999/2000: Entering the 21st Century* (Oxford University Press 1999)

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

